

MEDICAL SCIENCES

MEDICAL WORLDWIDE IN THE CREATION OF FAMOUS POETS AND THINKERS OF ANCIENT AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract

The study of the history of world medicine is directly related to the in-depth study of the ethnic composition, way of life, geographical environment, as well as the historical and cultural development of large and small peoples who lived on earth and now exist. The great achievements in all fields of science in the tenth and thirteenth centuries formed the basis of further scientific progress. In Azerbaijan, as in the whole East, all fields of science are poetry, philosophy, science, architecture, medicine and medicine, mathematics, geometry, theology, law, etc. Developed. Scientists and specialists educated in the central cities of the East (Cairo, Alexandria, Baghdad, Tabriz, Samarkand, Bukhara, Isfahan) cooperated scientifically. Among them, Abul-ula Ganjavi, Falafi Shirvani, Ibrahim Ibn Ali Najjar Khagani, Ibn Yusif, Sheikh Ilyas, Nizami Ganjavi, Qatran Tabrizi, Imameddin Nasimi, Omar Osman oglu and others entered the world cultural treasury.

Keywords: medicine, poetry, philosophy, medieval Azerbaijan, poet.

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Tabrizd where Qatran Tabrizi was also buried Tomb of Poets

Shirvani, Ibrahim Ibn Ali Najjar Khagani, Ibn Yusif, Sheikh Ilyas, Nizami Ganjavi, Qatran Tabrizi, Imameddin Nasimi, Omar Osman oglu and others entered the world cultural treasury[4, 5].

Qatran Tabrizi, one of the famous poets of medieval Azerbaijan 1012-in Tabriz near Shadi-abad was born in the village. The poet's full name is Abu Mansur Qatran Jili Azerbaijan. Qatran is the author of "Tovsname", "Gushname", "Vamig and Ezra", as well as a large divan consisting mainly of poems.

Afzaladdin Khagani

The great thinker and poet Khagani Shirvani, who was born in Shamakhi, the ancient land of Azerbaijan, has a wide literary activity in medicine.

I got inspiration from medical science.

That is why I am a Socrates of the realm of words.

My mind has taken a share of a thousand and one seas

I met the grass from Mount Qaf.

Speaking about his uncle in one of his poems, Khagani writes: "He explained to me in a very easy way what 'one', 'two', 'three', 'four', 'five' mean. 'Five' are members of the senses." four "-the beginnings of the world-are water, air, fire and earth," "three" -is inorganic nature, "two" -is body and soul, "one" -is God. " Apparently, such healing centers in Azerbaijan

has become very popular. So that, "Mahsati and Amir Ahmed" in the saga Ganja The hospital is described as a "hospital". There, patients line up to see a doctor [6].

It is no coincidence that Khagani, who continues the tradition of Omar Osman's son, writes: hypocrisy, enmity, and lying"

It is very interesting that Azerbaijani poets and ashugs skillfully described the achievements of medical figures and their miraculous medicines in their poems. The medical meetings of the genius Nizami, who gave incomparable works to the treasury of world culture, his advice on prophylaxis, his attitude to the theory of humor, testify to his deep acquaintance with medicine [2]. .

Ilyas Yusif oglu Nizami Ganjavi was born in 1141 in Ganja, the oldest cultural center of our country.

It is known from his works that the poet created a great divan and became famous as an author of ghazals and poems. Nizami's lyrics are distinguished by high artistry, secular attitude to love, humanistic thoughts about human destiny. However, Nizami entered the history of world literature as the author of "Khamasa" (Five), consisting of five poems ("Treasure of Secrets", "Khosrov and Shirin", "Leyli and Majnun", "Seven beauties", "Alexander's letter"), which he wrote in the form of a proverb [9]. .

Nizami Ganjavi died on March 12, 1209 in the city of Ganja.

In many works of Nizami Ganjavi, medical meetings in the field of humor and prophylaxis, diet are astonishing. At the same time, his complaints about time and tyrants, the law of non-disappearance of substances testify to his encyclopedic scholarship. Nizami Ganjavi says about health and medicine:

*If he loses his temper, if his way,
Health is very difficult to capture.
Do not eat or drink too much with appetite,
There will be a sweet smile on his lips.
No one gets hot from a little food, but
Hundreds die every day from eating too much,*

look.

Nizami Ganjavi (1141-1209)

by Narrow-mindedness there was also a medical academy. The Shamakhi poet Seyid Imadeddin Abu Said Hussein Nasimi, after studying the relevant sciences of the eminent scholars of the VIII-IX centuries AH, reached the service of Fazlullah Naimi (Hij. 796 m) and reached the highest levels of spirituality, benefiting from his education and training. The analysis of the poet's works shows that Nasimi was

*It is haraam to comb the grass,
To make the body need medicine*

Nizami writes in "Iskendername":
*A doctor who cures pain is never
Did not find and will not find a cure for death*

The law of non-disappearance of substances in the world is said to have been discovered by Lavoisier and Lomonosov. In fact, the great Nizami explained the law of non-disappearance of substances long before them in the following verse:

*Our servants who rot in the ground
Destroys, changes, does not destroy repair,
If it stays in place, it will be destroyed*

*When it comes together, it comes to life again.
Things spilled on the ground completely
He rises from the ground again*

From Islam Later, Shamakhi became one of the major cultural centers. There were many schools, madrasas, poetry and music festivals famous all over the East, and rich public and private libraries. A little outside the capital, Ointment famous poet in the so-called place Xaqani Shirvaninin uncle-scientist and doctor Kafiaddincreated [13].

able to get a perfect education in Shamakhi to meet the requirements of the best universities of that time. O, classic East and ancient Greek philosophy, as well as a deep knowledge of literature, a close knowledge of the basics of Islam and Christianity, medicine, astronomy and astrology, mathematic and logic had mastered his sciences. He learned languages so well that Azerbaijan Persian and Arabic he could write equally beautiful poems.

Imadeddin Nasimi (1369-1417)

Prominent medieval Azerbaijani poet and thinker Mohammad Suleyman oglu Fuzuli was born in 1494 in the Iraqi city of Karbala. He is known as one of the greatest representatives of the divan genre in the history of Azerbaijani-Turkish literature. He is often referred to as Baghdadi. But the poet in Baghdad not famous near him Karbala He is known to have been born in Karbala [8].

Fuzuli in three languages ghazal, in verse, sanctuary, clause, experience, rübai, continent, jamand so on. wrote. His philosophical poems, "Seven Glasses", "Anisul-Qalb", "Health and Disease" are the products of old age. He collected his poems as a separate work and compiled them into a book, composing divans in Turkish, Persian and Arabic.

Fuzuli was acquainted with ancient Greek and Eastern philosophy. His philosophical views are reflected in his work "Matlul-etiqa", written mainly in Arabic. Fuzuli is here Aristotle, Plato, Empedocles, Democritus and the ideas of other Greek philosophers, influenced by the philosophical heritage of al-Nizam.

The medical outlook of the great Azerbaijani poet Mohammad Fuzuli and his work gave a strong impetus to the development of medicine, as well as many other areas.

Genius Fuzuli's deep philosophical outlook, unparalleled medical imagination and sharp cognitive power allowed him to create an extremely sublime and imaginary, poetically unique work called "Health and Illness".

Mohammad Fuzuli describes the body of a healthy person with great enthusiasm and love, brings joy to the world with it and rejoices himself. Fuzuli explains the body's ability to fight the disease, shows that the cause of the disease depends on the composition and ratio of 4 body fluids. This work explains psychophysiological problems. Fuzuli's psychophysiological theory is consistent with the psychophysiological theory of IP Pavlov and PK Anoxin. His book "Health and Disease" fully explains this issue.

In his work "Health and Disease" Fuzuli for the first time explains his applause and gratitude to the Creator as the beauty of the scientific mind and the investment of the mind [12].

Muhammad Fuzuli (1494-1556)

Fuzuli came to the following conclusion after examining the medical and philosophical heritage of Hippocrates, the father of medicine, Sheikh-ur-Ra'is Ibn Sina and other physicians and scientists of the East, and weighing them on the scales of reason.

The juices and fluids that control the body and the health of the body (blood, mucus, bile and bile) are sometimes relevant and sometimes different.

The health of the body is ensured when the 4 fluids that own this land are in harmony with each other, that is, when their composition and proportions are stable. Otherwise, if the composition and proportions are disturbed, the body becomes ill.

The genius Fuzuli sees the violation of the composition and ratio of fluids in the violation of the relationship between nature and the body, that is, the composition of the organism corresponds to the composition of nature, the body must use a full range of fluids present in nature. Then the composition and ratio of liquids remain constant.

When these fluids circulate in the body, the body feels sweetness, bitterness, salinity and acidity. At the same time, they create dryness, moisture, heat and cold in the body. All this determines the "taste" of the body, that is, the absolute individual characteristics.

There are copies of Fuzuli's work "Health and Disease" in various libraries and museums under the names "Ruhnama", "Husnu-eshq". In a ghazal with the line "Doctor", Fuzuli sums up all his medical thoughts and writes:

*There is a punhan disease in my soul out of love,
O doctor!*

Please do not express my sorrow to the people, O doctor!

*Don't be offended, take your hope from Fuzuli,
Who is not sick, O doctor!*

The books written by the great thinker Fuzuli on the philosophy, science and medicine of the Azerbaijani people in the 16th century were a great event.

Fuzuli's writings covered great scientific questions. Fuzuli was deeply interested in natural and medical sciences. His writings "Talking to Nature", "Health and Disease" can be mentioned. Fuzuli writes about the beauty of the nature of his native land in his book "Conversation with Nature".

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